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Overall Framework of the Foundations and Pillars of Sustainable Development for Local Communities (Damietta Governorate Model)

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Abstract

Egypt as a developing country aims to promote sustainability among its various sectors. Noticing the need for promoting better life among local communities, as the corner stone for promoting sustainable development, the government has initiated a number of private and public attempts that aimed for utilizing the local communities as a catalyst for promoting sustainability.

After 3 decades of real attempts for promoting local sustainability approaches most of the attempts has failed to achieve its objectives. The research aims to introduce an innovative practical approach that would have the ability to overcome the defined deficiencies of the existing approaches and to practically promote sustainability among local communities. The research methodology will depend on an analytical comparative analysis of the existing sustainability local communities frameworks based on which the deficiency and contributions of the current situation can be defined. Then based on theoretical analysis the research is to innovate and introduce a new approach for promoting local sustainable communities, 'Foundation and Pillars for Sustainable local communities' (FPSLC). The developed framework was then applied to Damietta Governorate as a case study where it was tested and proven.

The research developed frame work is requested by the development agencies in Egypt to enable the achievement outputs and result of this research can be summarized in the formulation of the conceptual framework for sustainable development and mechanisms leading to realizing self sufficiency within the competitive industries through the introduced pillars of development.

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Keywords

Sustainable local communities; Sustainability foundations and pillars; Local communities models

1. Preface

Damietta is one of the windows of Egypt on the coast of the Mediterranean Sea, where the north of the delta is located on the east bank of the Nile River and the city of Damietta is the capital of the province 15 km from the estuary of the river, which is a peninsula populated by the Mediterranean to the north and Lake Manzala to the east; Delta and its plains.

The relative importance of urban and rural areas in the governorate is represented by the urban areas in the existing city of Damietta and the new city of Damietta near the new Damietta port which is one of the most important elements supporting the city in activating the interaction between the city and the scope of the influence of the port and providing huge opportunities for investment in all fields (Chemical - Furniture - Paper industries - Engineering industries - Packaging - Storage) both in the industrial zone or the coastal zone as well as in the field of housing. The new city is considered a development pole that integrates with the existing city to solve the problems of the governorate and the existing city of providing jobs and new extension areas and revitalizing the industry. Damietta city's urban wall is being completed with the establishment of the Furniture City as an integrated industrial zone for furniture industries to enter international markets. The rural area of the governorate is integrated into the economic activities of the governorate. The governorate is considered as an integrated development unit for a number of industries, mainly the furniture industry. Figure (1) shows the location of Damietta Governorate in Delta Egypt.

Figure 1. Shows the location of Damietta Governorate in Delta Egypt

2. Research Problem:

Egypt as a developing country aims to promote sustainability among its various sectors. Noticing the need for promoting better life among local communities, as the corner stone for promoting sustainable development, the government has initiated a number of private and public attempts that aimed for utilizing the local communities as a catalyst for promoting sustainability.

After 3 decades of real attempts for promoting local sustainability approaches most of the attempts has failed to achieve its objectives. The research problem can be summarized in the need to introduce an innovative practical approach that would have the ability to overcome the defined deficiencies of the existing approaches and to practically promote sustainability among local communities to enable the successful application of the new approaches of the recently announced Egypt's 2030 strategy and achieve its objectives.

3. Research Aims and Objectives:

Thus this research paper aims at developing an overall framework of the foundations and pillars of sustainable development for local communities using Damietta governorate Model as a case study. This will achieve the

main outputs and result of this research can be summarized in the formulation of the conceptual framework for sustainable development and mechanisms leading to realizing self sufficiency within the competitive industries through the introduced pillars of development.

4. Research Methodology:

4.1. This research will proceed in accordance with the following methodology:

First Analysis of industries with competitive advantage will be presented with special focus on the local industries of Damietta Governorate as the subject for the case study to determine the basic required elements

The methodology will then proceed to defining the pillars and criteria for sustainable development of Damietta's community including the role of the main actors in the development of industry

This will be followed by studying the extent of integration among export industries within the framework of a single production format, with emphasis on the production units of the furniture industry.

The research will then proceed to understanding the functional specialized units for the furniture industry of Damietta Governorate, which includes both urban and rural areas and the extent of benefiting from the characteristics and culture of the local community to activate these units.

The research will then climax with developing a comprehensive framework and pillars for the sustainable development of local communities.

4.2. 1. Development of Damietta Furniture Industry as a local Industry With Global Competitiveness

4.2.1. Craft Industries

Damietta is famous for its high quality and taste, which matches the latest international designs. Damietta produces almost two-thirds of the furniture production in Egypt. The total annual production is 375,000 rooms (bedroom, dining room, salon and pantry), as well as kitchens and chairs. In addition to industrial and commercial activities, the daily production is estimated to be around 2 million pounds. Due to the quality of the furniture product and its compatibility with the global development of this industry, Damietta furniture has found a place on the export map since Years to compete with world production and surpass it since ancient times.

Damietta is famous for the textile industry because of its proximity to the areas designated for the cultivation of the finest cotton and linen and for the skill of its international people in this industry, the boats that run to the old port of Damietta were loaded with cedar wood for the manufacture of ships and furniture and are loaded with hand-made textiles. It was used by merchants from everywhere to buy textiles and embroidered fabrics. Damietta Spinning & Weaving Company is the head of Damietta textile industry. It is a large edifice whose production covers the local market and a large part of the production is exported to Europe and America. (Planning, 2015)

4.2.2. Development of furniture Industry Thought in Damietta

Development of invested and working capital during the period 2003 – 2009 , the working capital and investor of the furniture industry in Damietta grew from 2003 to 2009, with working capital reaching about LE 3.8 billion, while the invested capital reached LE 3.5 billion, figure (2) shows Development of invested and working capital during the period 2003 – 2009 . The value was reduced from 2010 to 2016.

Figure 2. Development of Invested and working Capital during the Period 2003 – 2009

- The furniture industry in Egypt is mainly concentrated in Damietta governorate in El-Jawh El-Bahr, as it produces nearly two-thirds of the production of wood furniture in Egypt with high quality and high taste that matches the latest designs.
- Damietta city is one of the best cities in the production and manufacture of furniture at the level of Egypt and has a global role (export)
- The furniture industry in Damietta province depends on the wood industries through factories for the production of wood, alpakash, factories for the production of veneer wood, and factories for the production of accessories for furniture, handles, paints, paints and other furniture.
- The total annual production of 375 thousand rooms between (sleeping, dining, salon, and entra) as well as the production of kitchens and chairs and the work of nearly 100 thousand workers as well as industrial and commercial assistance and estimated daily production of nearly two million pounds of Egyptian. (AUFSD, Association for the Upgrading Furniture Sector in Domietta, 2014)
- The volume of Egyptian exports was expected to reach one billion dollars in 2017-2018. Figure (3) shows The exports of furniture industry to 1 billion \$.

Figure 3. Exports of furniture industry to 1 billion \$

4.2.3. Factors Affecting the Increase in the Rate of Industrial Production

- The main reasons for the boom in the rate of increase in income entry of the industry modernization program in Damietta. Operating more than 10 new factories in New Damietta and other factories under construction.
- Industry Modernization Program: The Egyptian Ministry of Industry aims to leapfrog huge leaps towards rapid growth and competition at the international level.
- Industrial modernization program: which covers all small and medium industrial activities and is not limited to a certain number of manufacturers, but includes all the manufacturers of Egypt in various industries, including the implementation of a comprehensive program to develop the furniture industry based on the land of Egypt in Damietta or elsewhere where the program aims in the first phase Development of 70 furniture facilities in Egypt.
- The exhibition of permanent furniture products in Damietta is one of the start-ups of the modernization of the Egyptian furniture industry and its requirements. Some 120 companies from various Egyptian companies working in the furniture industry are participating in the exhibition, stressing the need to benefit from the Egyptian industries which have a good international reputation. Italy, France, Germany, England, Austria and others
- The modernization program for the furniture industry in cooperation with Damietta governorate has created a spirit of cooperation and coordination between Damietta furniture manufacturers, which facilitated the accurate diagnosis of their problems and the development of suitable and immediate solutions.
- The exhibitions organized by the Egyptian Industrial Modernization Center or in which it participates have a positive impact on the Egyptian industry, where it succeeded in concluding direct and indirect contracts between several Egyptian factories and international markets, especially that they enjoy international quality specifications and high tastes and favorable prices. The results are accurate to ensure the maximum benefit of these exhibitions for the Egyptian furniture products.
- The modernization is not limited to industrial establishments, but extends to quality programs and calibrations and testing laboratories as one of the most important elements of increasing the exports of many Egyptian factories working in the field of furniture industry.
- The Egyptian Ministry of Industry maintains relations with representatives of international companies for furniture investors who are invited to watch Egyptian furniture products and the advantages and possibilities of Egyptian furniture, especially in quality, taste and price.
- For its part, Damietta Governorate, the main producer of the furniture industry in Egypt, is implementing a comprehensive plan for the development of this important activity and the establishment of a committee that was later developed an association on behalf of the Damietta Furniture Development Association, praising the role played by the modernization program to improve the quality and tastes of these products and facilitate their presence in international markets and from The opening of the Faculty of Applied Arts in Damietta will receive about 200 students to provide skilled workers able to absorb the modern technology of this industry.
- The Industrial Modernization Center is developing strategic plans to promote the furniture industry, which represents one of the main industries met by the industry modernization program. Damietta Governorate alone includes about 35,000 production factories and workshops. About 75% of the Egyptian furniture exporters go to the Middle East, Europe and the USA.
- The Damietta furniture industry is part of the regional programs implemented by the modernization program. The Damietta Center of Excellence program includes the provision of export development services for medium-sized enterprises in Damietta's furniture sector, financed by € 197,300 for 15 furniture manufacturers in Damietta.

- The Industrial Modernization Center is given great priority to make a real breakthrough in the Egyptian furniture industry and to benefit from the huge potential of Egypt. It organizes exhibitions and hosts a group of international experts to provide expertise and transfer of export expertise to international markets. The factories that participated in the exhibitions organized by the program achieved large export contracts, Its production lines for more than a coming season.
- Egypt attaches particular importance to the need to rely on national industrialization and in national factories such as government factories or private sector factories. This includes the furniture industry in order to achieve and raise the competitiveness of the Egyptian industry to deal with foreign markets in the framework of the Egyptian European Partnership Agreement.
- 885 companies in the modernization program, including 65 companies from the city of Damietta to develop the furniture industry. It is updated. Within the factories and focuses on the development of production processes and the introduction of quality systems and management training and professional employment and the composition of marketing devices.
- Eighty plants have been developed to comply with international standards and 260 companies have participated in training programs for human capacity development in senior and middle management and industrial management. In addition, 4 service centers were set up in 10th of Ramadan, 6th of October, Alexandria and Damietta. The modernization program is being held in Damietta with the Association of Furniture Exporters to develop them through the establishment of a technological center, design center, training center and showrooms in European countries.

4.3. The Integration of Export Industries in the Context of a Production Format Represented in the Production Units of the Furniture Industry

The market for Damietta furniture has witnessed a big boom over the last few years. Statistics show that the furniture industry in the last five years progressed at a high annual rate Indicators of the rate of increase in income in 2001 the income of the export of furniture Damietta about 36 million dollars and in 2005 amounted to income of 129 million and 500 thousand dollars. In 2008, income amounted to \$ 280 million. (Gouvernorate, 2017) Total exports in 2014 of furniture \$ 1600 million and imports \$ 423 million has increased consumption by 16% in 2015, exports rose by 35% and imports rose by While production increased by 12% (Elbangay, 2016)

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia tops the list of importing countries, where the percentage of imported Egyptian furniture products 25% of the total exports of furniture in the country, while the United Arab Emirates ranked second place by 6%. Italy is imported from Egypt with a value of 17.2 million US dollars and exports in Italy amounted to about 7%.

China is a major source of furniture imports in the Egyptian market, accounting for 39% of the total furniture imports. The value of these imports is \$ 55 million, while Asia and the Middle East together account for 55% Of all furniture imports to Egypt. Germany is a supplier to Egypt, with 9% of total furniture imports valued at \$ 13 million and the United States the third largest foreign exporter of furniture to Egypt worth \$ 11 million (Elbangay, 2016)

4.3.1. Functional Specialization at the Level of Local Units of the Governorate

Through the analysis of the quality of industries in the province, the province was divided into stages of production of the furniture industry where there are dedicated areas as follows:

- The processing areas are represented by the port area and the adjacent irrigation sector in the western part of the governorate.
- Special areas of the manufacturing process and concentrated in the south of the province in rural units.

- Areas to finalize the product in the center of the province in the provinces of small cities such as the city of Faraskur and the city of kindergarten and the city of Abu Gharib and Zarqa and the rural units of these cities.
- Areas of marketing and manufacturing together concentrated in the territory of the city of Damietta, which is based on the branch of Damietta branch of Nile. (Gouvernorate, 2017) Figure (4) shows The functional specialization of furniture industry operations in Damietta Governorate.

4.3.2. Levels of Development Units

Figure 4. The functional specialization of furniture industry operations in Damietta Governorate

Industry levels can be classified into sub-production units as follows:

- Units for the manufacture of modern furniture is in the northern areas of the province of the cities: Damietta and Damietta new and Kafr Saad and Kafr al-Batikh.
- Secondary units for the traditional furniture industry in the western province near the Egyptian Delta
- Sub-units for the traditional furniture industry concentrated in the southeast of the province of the cities of Faraskur, kindergarten, Abu Ghaleb, Zarqa and Siro. Figure (5) shows the levels of specialization units for the furniture industry.

Figure 5. levels of specialization units for the furniture industry

4.3.3. Number of workshops and furniture factories in Damietta City and its employees.

- The presence of more than 35 thousand small workshops and some medium factories and spread in all cities of the province and employs in this industry more than 100 thousand workers and more than 10 thousand others frequented daily to maintain the province to work in this profession ..
- The production of large and medium factories in Damietta represents about 20% of the export production. The small workshops in all the cities and villages of the governorate numbering 35 thousand workshops represent 80% of the export production.
- A unique experiment in eliminating unemployment within the governorate. This experiment began to be spread throughout all educational stages. The most important of these is the furniture industry and the woodwork. Therefore, after graduating, the student has no obstacle to finding a job.
- There is a relationship between the distribution of the rate of growth of workshops geographically with the distribution of employment growth rate. (Gouvernorate, 2017) Figures (6) & (7) show the Growth of employment in the Damietta & the Growth of workshops maintained.

Figure 6. Growth of employment in the Damietta

Figure 7. Growth of workshops maintained

4.4. The Foundations and Pillars of Sustainable Development Units of Damietta Governorate

The economic activity in Damietta is one of the best economic patterns in the development process as it achieves economic growth because it is based on several foundations and pillars represented in the following:

- Spatial location of relative importance
- Community Culture of Damietta Governorate
- Private capital for industrial men in the governorate
- Management of the furniture industry
- The role of the parties in the industry
- Contribution to local and national output
- Local and global competition

4.4.1. The Relative Importance of Damietta Governorate Location

- The establishment of the new city of Damietta, where a new economic entity is subject to the law of new urban communities and have huge opportunities to invest in the coastal area or industrial area as well as investment in housing, in addition to the availability of places and land required for housing.
- The availability of skilled labor and also available many of the workers from the geographically close governorates, such as Dakahlia, Western, Eastern, Kafr Sheikh.
- The allocation of the industrial area in the new city of Damietta, with an area of 300 feddans located south of the new city of Damietta, in addition to an area of 250 feddans which is an extension of it. The industrial zone entered the actual production phase with many projects including food projects, chemical, furniture, paper industries, Engineering - Packing & Packaging - Storage, ...). A small complex for small industries within the area was also implemented and allocated on an area of 2916 square meters to provide opportunities for young artisans.
- The existence of the free industrial zone east of Damietta Port, with an area of 190 feddans located in the area between the navigational canal and Damietta port. It aims to create an industrial pool. This area was supplied with an electric capacity of 8 MW and a 400mm diameter plan of drinking water (Planning, Regional Plan of Damietta, 1996)
- The free storage area is located west of Damietta port with an area of 545 feddans and serves the port of Damietta and the industrial free zone east of the port.
- Damietta Port and its distinguished potential in providing depths that allow the reception of giant vessels and regular international shipping lines linking Damietta with Europe, North America and Far Eastern countries.
- The City of Furniture represents an important qualitative leap for the availability of furniture technology in Egypt. The company and the sons of Damietta hope that the city will become the new center for the furniture industry in the Middle East and Africa. The city is expected to make a major shift in the export of Egyptian furniture. The Egyptian product is the international, regional and local markets. The dream of the furniture city of Damietta is a true model of the will of the state in success. The city will be established according to the international standards in technology 3, the henningers, which are the first of the project's construction, were finished. The first one contains 22 workshops, a small factory and a new workshop center. To be a technological center for the development of the furniture industry, which includes a place to train manufacturers on the latest manufacturing methods and a chemical laboratory to test the quality of wood and the final product in addition to the laboratory of quality tests in the city.

- Detailed studies of the new furniture city (Office, 2015) have been carried out to ensure the comprehensive development of its industry through various industrial zones within the framework of the city's master plan. The project will be implemented in several phases, A medium and a complementary industries and other petrochemical industries for the manufacture of environmentally friendly products, in addition to the allocation of space for infrastructure projects, in addition to major marketing areas including one of the largest marketing exhibitions of furniture along the two sides of the city. Figures (8) & (9) show the image of Workshope in Furniutrue city & New Furniture City Master Plan.

Figure 8. Image of Workshops in Furniture city

Figure 9. New Furniture City Master Plan

4.4.2. Community culture

- There is an impact on the culture of the Damietta society on the development of the furniture industry, where the interdependence of the family members integration in the distribution of roles (marketing - industry - ...)
- The diversification of economic activities in the governorate between industrial activity and craftsmen (small industries) and tourists in addition to commercial activity and fishing, which affected the culture and characteristics of the community in Damietta Governorate.
- Damietta economic activity depends mainly on the human element as the most important resources owned by the province and for the population to be characterized by activity, love and work.
- Cultural and social heritage of the population, where workshops are located under the homes of children and children, which confirmed their skill in manufacturing and love to work in this area.
- Damietta is considered a large workshop in which all sectors of the society interact, considering the Damietta citizen as a small investor. The specialty of the Damietta society is in its culture and its influence on the

development of the furniture industry. In the current situation, there is an overlap of the Syrian bodies for residency in Damietta. In the industry and their entry as investors.

4.4.3. Private capital for the industrial men in the governorate

Industrialists are the owners of capital, which affects the revitalization of the movement of the furniture industry, which leads to ease of movement of capital among investors in Damietta. (Galad, 2014)

4.4.4. Management of the Furniture Industry:

- The impact of the new city of Damietta, the new port and the city of furniture (under construction) on strengthening the industry and opening markets in the Arabian Gulf, Europe and Africa. State intervention in the management system of the furniture industry in support of this special system.
- Development depends on small production units and the efforts of the governorate with the Social Fund to support these productive units and provide loans to craftsmen and provide production requirements. One of the fruits of these efforts was that Damietta has a permanent exhibition in the exhibition grounds in Cairo to showcase the furniture of high quality, taste and taste. The province has also gone a long way in exporting production to Arab countries.
- Providing services related to the existing industries to assist in the process of industrial development in the field of furniture industry such as (management of local affairs - training courses for young people, etc.)

4.4.5. Role of Parties in Industry

- Actors in the furniture industry are represented in the Furniture Development Association - the Association of Furniture Industry Investors - and the role of State industrial development centers. The role of the Association of Furniture Industry Investors in the development of industry and the intervention of the State as a supporter of the industry and opening exhibitions and markets for the furniture industry at the international and local levels.
- Services provided by the Industrial Modernization Center Damietta branch to Damietta furniture customers: Services provided by the State Modernization Center in the services group: quality, finance, information services, training, human resources, recruitment of experts, training needs, Energy saving, lending for modernization, production. Figure (10) shows the Technical Services provided by the Industrial Modernization Center Damietta branch to Damietta furniture customers.

Figure 10. Technical Services provided by the Industrial Modernization to Damietta furniture customers

4.4.6. Contribution to GDP:

The extent of the serious contribution of the furniture industry to the increase of the national and local product of the province.

4.4.7. Local and Global Competition:

Is there a role for the competition for the furniture industry at the local and global level, the impact of the furniture industry imported from China on the furniture industry in Damietta, are there mechanisms to meet the challenges of industry to reach global competition.

4.4.8. Examining the impact of factors for achieving sustainable development of local communities through an opinion survey (Questionnaire) (Questionnaire, 2017)

A survey was conducted for the concerned parties in Damietta Governorate (makers, workers, officials, traders, investors, etc.) to measure the main factors and pillars affecting the furniture industry through a set of basic and sub-variables. It measures the most important factors affecting the sustainability of Damietta furniture industry. The presence of the effect of whether or not to measure the degree of this effect is very strong, strong, average, admit, weak. These variables were as follows:

1. Impact of the site: includes a set of sub-elements is to measure the impact of the location on the Mediterranean Sea, the impact of the port on the increase of exports and imports and the impact of the role of New Damietta in the development of furniture industry)

2. Community Culture: Measuring the impact of the Damietta society culture on the development of the furniture industry, the interdependence of the family members, integration in the distribution of roles (marketing, industry, etc.). Damietta is considered a large workshop in which all segments of society interact, the specificity of the Damietta community in its culture of work and its impact on the development of the furniture industry, and measuring the acceptance of the Damietta society of other nationalities such as the Syrians and their entry as investors.

3. The movement of private capital and its impact on the furniture industry: Manufacturers are the owners of capital, which affects the revitalization of the movement of the furniture industry, measuring the freedom of movement of capital between investors, measuring Is there a restriction on the movement of investment in the country?

4. Management of the furniture industry: measuring the availability of private management among individuals, integration of production lines between urban and rural areas, the impact of the new city of Damietta and the new port on strengthening the industry and opening markets in the Arabian Gulf or Europe - Africa.

5. Role of Industry Parties: Is there an impact on the role of the Furniture Development Association on Industry and the Industrial Development Unit? Is there a role for the association of furniture industry investors in the development of industry? Is there an impact to support the state in opening exhibitions and markets for the furniture industry?

6. Contribution to GDP and GDP: Measuring the serious contribution of the furniture industry to increasing the national and local output of the governorate.

7. Local and global competition: Is there a role for competition for the furniture industry at the local (national) and global level, the impact of the furniture industry imported from China on the furniture industry in Damietta, are there mechanisms to meet the challenges of industry to reach global competition.

8. Free Opinion: Writing for other influential factors.

By SPSS program using the results of the sample for the availability of the effect of the variables that were included in the questionnaire form and analyzed statistically by the T-One-Sample Test (T-One-Sample Test), which is one of the important statistical tests used to test the differences between the averages of one sample or two samples, A

significant correlation was found between the variables (P-Value = 0.000), i.e., it can be based on these variables by more than 95%.

In measuring the degree of agreement between the responses of the sample on the importance of the effect of the main variables, shown in Table (1), the result of the analysis of the questionnaire indicates:

The consensus was that a variable (contribution to GDP and GDP) would affect Damietta governorate as a productive unit.

This variable is influenced by both the variables (site impact, community culture, private capital movement and its impact on the furniture industry), respectively, with a significant impact of more than 80% of the relationship.

The variables of (furniture industry management - the role of the parties in the industry - local and international competition) have the importance of medium impact in the relationship of Damietta governorate as a production unit amounting to about 77%.

Table 1. T-One-Sample Test- degree of agreement between the responses of the sample on the importance of the effect of the main variables

One-Sample Statistics		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
TRGAT	230	12.00	6.648	.438
FACTOR_ availability_ influence	230	.84	.364	.024

Table 2. agreement between the responses of the sample on the degree of influence of the main variables and the sub-result of the analysis of the questionnaire indicates

One-Sample Test	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
TRGAT	27.376	229	.000	12.000	11.14	12.86
FACTOR_ availability_ influence	35.129	229	.000	.843	.80	.89

In measuring the Degree of Agreement Between the Responses of the Sample on the Degree of Influence of the Main Variables and the Sub-result of the analysis of the Questionnaire Indicates:

There are three levels to the effect of the main variables (very strong - strong - average) as shown in Table (2). Where the variable (contribution to GDP and national) has the highest degree of influence in the relationship by 92%, while the variables (the role of parties to the industry - local and global competition) have the least impact in the relationship by 55%

The existence of four levels of the effect of the sub-variables ranged from (very strong - strong - average - acceptable - weak) as shown in Table (2). Where variables (presence of influence on the culture of the Damietta society on the development of the furniture industry, the presence of serious contribution to the furniture industry to increase the national and local output of the province) have the highest degree of impact in the relationship by 92%, while the variables (availability of private management among individuals, For other nationalities such as Syrians and their entry as investors in the furniture industry) had the least impact on the relationship by 28% and 36%, respectively due to the dependence of the furniture industry on independent economic entities and the non-entry of other nationalities in the field (most of the Syrians go to the food industry), according to the responses of the parties concerned.

Mechanisms of Damietta’s continuation as a unit produced by analyzing the views of the questionnaire:

- Continuing to support the efforts of the State in providing local and international exhibitions and providing means of transport for small manufacturers to transport goods to local exhibitions.
- Provide support for raw materials to help small workshops.

- Providing raw materials at the appropriate prices for the presence of huge qualified manpower in the furniture industry to support the opening of new workshops.
- Ensuring that the city of furniture is equipped with mechanisms that allow the employment of the young people of the governorate alongside the large factories.
- Activate the role of furniture associations to ensure sustainability of the industry.
- Development of human resources for employment in all fields (carpentry, engraving, etc.) entering the industrial process.
- Facilitating the procedures for obtaining licenses and providing information dissemination for export and providing transparency of this information.
- Not to overstate the taxation of small workshops to encourage the licensing of workshops and reduce the use of the State.
- Reducing customs duties on imported raw materials.
- Add new machines and new equipment to add a higher and better level of the product.
- Disruption or reduction of brokers in business transactions because of inconvenience to the seller and the buyer.
- Cooperation between investors and the state.
- Providing overseas markets for product display.
- Technological compatibility with the latest machines and machines abroad and providing them in the governorate for the development of industry.

5. Comprehensive framework for the foundations and pillars of local development and their role in achieving sustainable development

Building an integrated community framework-The community framework is one of the most important pillars of development. The community has industrial skills to take advantage of the Damietta model to promote the sustainable development of local communities.

Production framework of industrial activities

- Definition of the prevailing conditions of industrial productivity and levels at the level of the industrial sector and its various activities.
- Determine the factors that have the effectiveness in pushing productivity rates to the required levels.

Development and modernization framework

- Evaluating the policies adopted for modernization and development in all fields related to industrial activity: marketing administrative production.
- Defining the general frameworks for modernization policies Development at the spatial and sectorial level, this has an impact on the productivity and competitiveness of industrial activities.

Building a technological base

- Undermining the technological reality of the Egyptian industry and its problems.
- The foundations of providing scientific technological base in Damietta.
- Mechanisms for the development of technological base and labor support.
- Industries that qualify for the introduction of modern technology.

Competitiveness Support Framework

Supporting the competitiveness of Egyptian industrial facilities is one of the basic requirements for facing the globalization of the international economy driving the export rates of industrial products. It is therefore one of the main pillars not only for industrial development but also for supporting the national economy as a whole. Therefore, it is important to have policies and programs to develop the competitiveness of industrial products in general and export in particular at the level of different industrial sectors as a result of the various indicators governing the competitive capabilities, namely:

- Macroeconomic indicators.
- Sectorial indicators.
- Indicators of economic activities

The efficiency of the performance of auxiliary and service activities for industrial production

- Increase in spatial correlation rates through roads and means of communication between the main and secondary industrial centers between them and the sources of production requirements, marketing centers and sea and air ports.
- Cover the existing shortfall in the needs of the facility of electricity, water and sanitation for the existing industrial activities and provide future requirements in this regard.
- Integration of service activities covering the needs of industrial activities in all areas: productivity - marketing - financing, at the sectorial and spatial level.

Sustainable development as a determinant of industrial development directions

Within the general framework of industrial development strategies, it is important to define the basic requirements and conditions under which industrial development strategies must be adapted to address negative environmental impacts, and in this context the conservation of sustainable natural resources at the national and regional levels.

Continuous industrial development

- Means that development strategies have the mechanisms to develop escalating development rates covering consumption and productivity needs at the sectorial (industrial) and spatial (regions)
- The requirements and means for the continuous development of industrial activity should therefore be determined.

Maximizing the positive aspects of globalization and reducing its disadvantages

Globalization and its free trade in goods, services, labor and capital have become the ruling elements of the economies of the world, especially the developing ones, and Egypt's intervention in this context, the implications of which cannot be ignored. It is therefore important to identify the orientations of industrial development strategies capable of maximizing the advantages of globalization and those that limit their disadvantages.

- Adapting the structure of the economic activities, especially the export, as it is more integrated into the global economy.
- Provide the necessary incentives to attract foreign investment.
- The orientations of the general policies of the State towards the activation of external economic ties, especially in the Arab and African countries and the European Union, in addition to China and Southeast Asian countries.
- Finding ways that are compatible with the contribution of international giants in industrial development.
- Activation of policies to protect emerging industries and counter dumping.

Building an institutional regulatory framework for the management of economic resources for industrial development

- The effectiveness and achievement of the objectives of industrial development strategies depend on the existence of an institutional regulatory framework that ensures that policies are formulated for the general plans and programs that are achieved for the objectives of the industrial development strategies. This is in addition to coordination between the industrial sector and other economic sectors as well as between the different public and private sectors related to industrial activity.

Taking into account the following:

- 70% of the industrial investments and therefore the responsibility for achieving the economic development goals lie with the private sector.
- Activating the role of the state in guiding the general economic path and achieving balance and interdependence between the economic sectors and facing any deviations resulting from the economic practices of the private sector that have negative effects on the public interest.
- The role of local administration in the management of industrial development and providing a climate conducive to achieving its objectives.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1. Search Results

- The foundations and pillars of local development in various fields and their role in achieving sustainable development.
- Functional specialization (furniture industries), which are considered competitive industries in Damietta Governorate.
- Focus on local industry and independence (self-sufficiency)
- Achieving the principle of popular participation.
- Integration of the system of export industries within the framework of a single production format.
- Completion of manufacturing rings under the technology available and compatible with the type of industries (simple and labor intensive technology)

6.2. Recommendations

- Achieving the principle of preserving the environment (good environmental impact)
- Providing marketing and distribution centers (providing shopping centers / furniture and marketing exhibitions)
- Providing basic networks (ports - ...)
- All members of society benefit from development revenues
- Providing local and international marketing management and skills
- Providing an appropriate investment climate for investment
- Increasing the role of the private industrial sector in achieving the industrialization strategy
- Providing 30 thousand employment opportunities in the villages and cities of the province by 1500 industrial workers annually.
- Dependence on agricultural resources and local raw materials in manufacturing (food and textile industries) with the need to provide some raw materials from abroad such as wood, plastic, building materials and mineral materials to form
- Link the industry to the local market and the needs of the population and interest in export
- Develop and update existing industry development programs
- Adopting the industries based in the centers of the province: wood, textile, food and engineering
- Dependence on labor-intensive industries, the most important of which are small industries and light industries, about 30% of the size of the industrial and crafts industry, 50% in terms of the number of workers.

6.3. Research resulting concepts

- Comprehensive Framework: A framework based on multiple subsectors to achieve the integrated development framework.
- Sustainable development: refers to development (economic, environmental, social) that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs and sustainable development is not a consistent state of harmony, but the process of change and exploitation of resources, investment orientation, direction of technological development, Which are in line with future needs as well as current needs.
- Competitive industries: industries that have the ability to compete in terms of quality and internal efficiency in the use of resources to ensure the conditions of survival and achieve economic return.
- Self-sufficiency: is that a country depends on its own possibilities to obtain its consumer and investment goods, in order to reduce the level of political and economic dependence of other countries and thus achieve a higher degree of independence in its decisions and international and internal positions. Self-sufficiency does not in any way mean stopping or cutting off trade with other countries, but preparing and securing national conditions and conditions to achieve higher profitability of economic exchange through the channels of international division of labor in order to develop local production quantitatively and qualitatively. Consumer and investment citizens. On the other hand, this new situation leads to a high level of economic and social welfare in general.

- The pillars of development: The basic rules on which the community depends on the work of development (such as technology, employment, infrastructure, services, etc.)
- Sustainable Development Units: A unit of integrated functional specialties to achieve economic development as a result of geographical location factors and social, cultural and environmental characteristics as sustainable factors for the development of local units.

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